

Supporting Information for

Seminatural areas act as reservoirs of genetic diversity for crop pollinators and natural enemies across Europe

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Contents:

Supplementary methods

METHODS S1 Genomic data filtering and assembling

Supplementary tables

TABLE S1 Genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) between populations of *Coccinella septempunctata*

TABLE S2 Genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) between populations of *Andrena flavipes*

Supplementary figures

FIGURE S1 Satellite images for each sampling site

FIGURE S2 Number of reads per individual for *Coccinella septempunctata* before and after different quality filtering steps

FIGURE S3 Number of reads per individual for *Andrena flavipes* before and after different quality filtering steps

FIGURE S4 Log probability of the data and the magnitude of ΔK for Bayesian clustering analyses in STRUCTURE

FIGURE S5 Results of genetic assignments based on the Bayesian method implemented in the program STRUCTURE

References

Supplementary methods

METHODS S1 Genomic data filtering and assembling

We used the different programs distributed as part of the STACKS v. 1.35 pipeline (*process_radtags*, *ustacks*, *cstacks*, *sstacks*, and *populations*) and default parameters to assemble our sequences into *de novo* loci and call genotypes (Catchen et al., 2011; Catchen et al., 2013; Hohenlohe et al., 2010). We demultiplexed and filtered reads for overall quality using the program *process_radtags*, retaining reads with a Phred score > 10 (using a sliding window of 15%), no adaptor contamination, and that had an unambiguous barcode and restriction cut site. We screened raw reads for quality with FASTQC v. 0.11.5 (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>) and trimmed all sequences to 180-bp using TRIMMOMATIC v. 0.36 (Bolger et al., 2014) in order to remove low-quality reads near the 3' ends. We assembled filtered reads *de novo* into putative loci with the program *ustacks*. We set the minimum stack depth (m) to three and allowed a maximum distance of two nucleotide mismatches (M) to group reads into a "stack". We used the "removal" (r) and "deleveraging" (d) algorithms to eliminate highly repetitive stacks and resolve over-merged loci, respectively. We identified single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) at each locus and called genotypes using a multinomial-based likelihood model that accounts for sequencing errors (Catchen et al., 2011; Catchen et al., 2013; Hohenlohe et al., 2010), with the upper bound of the error rate (ϵ) set to 0.2. A conservative upper bound was selected for the error parameter, as these models have been developed primarily for higher coverage data. Using a conservative bound was preferred over the unbounded model, which has been shown to underestimate heterozygotes (Catchen et al., 2013; e.g., Papadopoulou & Knowles, 2015). After the different quality filtering steps by *process_radtags* and *ustacks*, we retained for downstream analyses those samples with >300k reads (Figures S2 and S3). Then, we built a catalogue of loci using the *cstacks* program, with loci recognized as homologous across individuals if the number of nucleotide mismatches between consensus sequences (n) was ≤ 2 . Finally, we matched each individual data against this catalogue using the program *sstacks* and exported output files in different formats for subsequent analyses using the program *populations*. The choice of different filtering and assembling thresholds has a little impact on the obtained inferences (e.g., González-Serna et al., 2019; Ortego et al., 2018). For this reason, unless otherwise indicated, we exported only the first SNP per RAD locus, and retained loci with a minimum stack depth ≥ 5 ($m = 5$) and that were represented in at least 75% of the populations ($p = 9$ for *C. septempunctata* and $p = 6$ for *A. flavipes*) and 50% of the individuals within each population ($r = 0.5$). We used the option *relatedness2* in VCFTOOLS to calculate the relatedness among all pairs of genotyped individuals and to exclude the possibility that we had sampled close relatives within each locality (Danecek et al., 2011; Manichaikul et al., 2010). All pairs of genotyped individuals from *C. septempunctata* had negative relatedness values (ranging from -0.83 to -0.07), which excludes the possibility of a close relationship (Manichaikul et al., 2010). In the case of *A. flavipes*, two individuals from Denmark collected in the seminatural site had relatedness values compatible with a close relationship (relatedness = 0.17) and we only retained one of them (the one with the highest sequencing depth) for subsequent analyses. The final datasets contained 102 and 60 unrelated individuals of *C. septempunctata* and *A. flavipes*, respectively (Table 1).

Supplementary tables

TABLE S1 Pairwise F_{ST} values (below the diagonal) and their corresponding p -values (above the diagonal) for populations of *Coccinella septempunctata* sampled in agricultural and seminatural landscapes. Significance of pairwise F_{ST} values was determined with Fisher's exact tests after 10,000 permutations, as implemented in ARLEQUIN v. 3.5. None pairwise F_{ST} value was significant after false discovery rate adjustment (FDR) to control for multiple tests (FDR of 5%, $q < 0.05$). Negative F_{ST} values are reported as zero. Sample size (n) for each population is given in parentheses. Population codes as described in Table 1.

	EE (agr.) ($n = 10$)	EE (nat.) ($n = 8$)	DK (agr.) ($n = 8$)	DK (nat.) ($n = 10$)	NL (agr.) ($n = 8$)	NL (nat.) ($n = 8$)	GB (agr.) ($n = 8$)	GB (nat.) ($n = 8$)	HU (agr.) ($n = 8$)	HU (nat.) ($n = 10$)	CH (agr.) ($n = 8$)	CH (nat.) ($n = 8$)
EE (agr.) ($n = 10$)	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
EE (nat.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
DK (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
DK (nat.) ($n = 10$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
NL (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
NL (nat.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
GB (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
GB (nat.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
HU (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999	>0.999
HU (nat.) ($n = 10$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999	>0.999
CH (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–	>0.999
CH (nat.) ($n = 8$)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	–

TABLE S2 Pairwise F_{ST} values (below the diagonal) and their corresponding p -values (above the diagonal) for populations of *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural and seminatural landscapes. Significance of pairwise F_{ST} values was determined with Fisher's exact tests after 10,000 permutations, as implemented in ARLEQUIN v. 3.5. Statistically significant values after false discovery rate adjustment (FDR) to control for multiple tests (FDR of 5%, $q < 0.05$) are indicated in bold. Negative F_{ST} values are reported as zero. Sample size (n) for each population is given in parentheses. Population codes as described in Table 1.

Code	DK (agr.) ($n = 8$)	DK (nat.) ($n = 6$)	NL (agr.) ($n = 8$)	NL (nat.) ($n = 7$)	CH (agr.) ($n = 8$)	CH (nat.) ($n = 8$)	ES (agr.) ($n = 10$)	ES (nat.) ($n = 5$)
DK (agr.) ($n = 8$)	–	0.005	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.001
DK (nat.) ($n = 6$)	0.030	–	0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.001	<0.001	0.003
NL (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.097	0.141	–	0.990	0.962	0.998	<0.001	0.001
NL (nat.) ($n = 7$)	0.106	0.131	0.000	–	0.727	0.953	<0.001	0.002
CH (agr.) ($n = 8$)	0.115	0.119	0.000	0.000	–	0.675	<0.001	0.001
CH (nat.) ($n = 8$)	0.112	0.113	0.000	0.000	0.001	–	<0.001	0.001
ES (agr.) ($n = 10$)	0.438	0.444	0.353	0.366	0.368	0.367	–	>0.999
ES (nat.) ($n = 5$)	0.398	0.424	0.309	0.310	0.290	0.281	0.000	–

Supplementary figures

FIGURE S1 Satellite images for each sampling site, including an agricultural and a nearby seminatural plot in seven European countries. Red dots indicate the center of the sampling site and correspond to the geographical coordinates given in Table 1. Images were retrieved from Google Earth Pro (© 2023 Google). A general map overview of study site locations is presented in Figure 2.

FIGURE S2 Number of reads per individual for *Coccinella septempunctata* before and after different quality filtering steps by STACKS. The total height of the bars represents the total number of raw reads obtained for each individual. Within each bar, the dark red color represents the reads that were discarded by *process_radtags* due to low quality, adapter contamination or ambiguous barcode and light red color represents the reads that were discarded by *ustacks* after filtering out repetitive elements and reads that did not comply the different criteria required to create a “stack”. Green color represents the number of retained reads used to identify homologous loci. Population codes as described in Table 1.

FIGURE S3 Number of reads per individual for *Andrena flavipes* before and after different quality filtering steps by STACKS. The total height of the bars represents the total number of raw reads obtained for each individual. Within each bar, the dark red color represents the reads that were discarded by *process_radtags* due to low quality, adapter contamination or ambiguous barcode and light red color represents the reads that were discarded by *ustacks* after filtering out repetitive elements and reads that did not comply the different criteria required to create a “stack”. Green color represents the number of retained reads used to identify homologous loci. Population codes as described in Table 1.

FIGURE S4 Mean (\pm SD) log probability of the data ($\text{LnPr}(X|K)$) over 10 runs of STRUCTURE (left axes, black dots and error bars) for each value of K and the magnitude of ΔK (right axes, blue triangles) of analyses for populations of (A) *Coccinella septempunctata* and (B-C) *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural and nearby seminatural landscapes from different countries. Analyses for *Andrena flavipes* were performed for (B) all populations jointly and (C) excluding populations from Spain.

FIGURE S5 Results of genetic assignments based on the Bayesian method implemented in the program STRUCTURE ($K = 2-5$) for populations of (A) *Coccinella septempunctata* and (B, C) *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural (agr.) and nearby seminatural (nat.) landscapes from different countries. Analyses for *A. flavipes* were performed for (B) all populations jointly and (C) excluding populations from Spain. Analyses are based on a random subset of 10,000 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Each individual is represented by a vertical bar, which is partitioned into K colored segments showing the individual's probability of belonging to the cluster with that color. Thin vertical black lines separate individuals from different populations. Population codes as described in Table 1.

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